

Love Across the Miles

(Acrostic Poem)

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Be honest to our relationship even if we're not together
 Every day I miss you because we're too far from each other; but
 No one can stop my love for you,
 Just be simple and show me the real you.
 It's not easy to trust but we need to,
 Enjoy your life and remember, I'm always here for you.
 Be positive in whatever you do!
 Our relationship may not our priority; because
 Remember we need to give more time to our family; and
 Remember without them we're not here where we stand today.
 Our relationship, I know it will be our priority someday,
 More time for each other as we share our moments everyday
 Everything we're wishing for might happen; I can be yours and you'll be
 mine
 Of course, we just need to wait for the right time.